

***SOCIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE MANAGEMENT AND
DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL INFRASTRUCTURE IN SMALL CITIES***

Kayumov Kakhramon Nozimjonovich

Department of social work

Docent, sociology

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

ANNOTATION

This article examines the problem of the mechanisms of management and development of the social infrastructure of small cities on the basis of the results of sociological research. Today, the development of small cities occupies an important place in the life of the country's socio-political life. From this point of view, the results of the sociological study cited by the author in this article and its significance are relevant.

Sociologically, the study and scientific research of small cities in different countries of the world is relevant and significant. Through sociological studies, the study of small towns can be divided into the following conditional 3 groups. These are:

1. Foreign School of sociology;
2. Former Union sociology;
3. Sociology of the independence period.

First team. In the studies of the foreign School of sociology, the processes of demography, migration, urbanization of the world were studied. In particular, the Russian American sociologist scientist P.Sorokin introduced the theory of social stratification to sociology in 1927. Social stratification is used to describe the "openness" or "closeness" of groups and one whole society. At the same time social applied the concept of mobility. Social mobility can also be calculated according to

the gender of individuals, the level of education, the "sanity coefficient", the nationality, race, residence of which resides in a city, small city or village, the corresponding coefficients between the quantitative indicators of social mobility individuals. With the help of determining the level of social mobility, one or another society is divided into "traditional", "modern", "industrial", "post-industrial" society manifestations . It is in this view that most of the cellulose of social mobility processes occurs in cities, given that societies exist in cities or small cities.

The occurrence of a city and a small city is the result of urbanization processes. Changes in the social status of individuals, an increase in their level of knowledge, the economic development of territories, transformation into cultural centers, improvement or deterioration of the natural environment are the reasons for the emergence of small cities. The duration of such processes is small, medium, large, large and megacities bring cities to the surface.

In Pierre Burde's macrosociological theory, capital resources are seen as a central concept. Burde distinguishes three main types of human capital: economic (understood mainly as income and property), social (understood mainly as interpersonal social relations) and cultural (education, upbringing, beliefs, culture, traditions and values). The presence of capital resources in society can be determined in two ways – quantitative and structural. Individual socialization agents can have more or less the same amount of capital as well as it can be structured in different proportions. Accordingly, while two different "agents" have the same amount of Capital, One will have more cultural capital and the other will have more economic capital .

The second group shows monographs written within the framework of the former Union, general historical data on cities of different levels in different regions of the Republic in scientific research, their place in economic and geographical terms, demographic processes from the point of view of managing the centralized national economy social infrastructure of the Soviet state. In the

former arrangement, however, sociology was not developed as a science, but as a governing instrument serving a political interest. As a result, the work of that time did not dwell in detail on problems in the socio-economic and spiritual-cultural spheres. That is, the main focus in the research carried out in this direction is limited to general information about the location and nature of small cities, and the problems associated with the development of their economic, social infrastructure are not mentioned.

Literature belonging to the third group was published mainly during the independence of our country, and in many of these publications, attention was paid to issues related to the management of the social infrastructure of large and medium-sized cities. "In the sociological research carried out during this period, new theoretical foundations have been created for the study of social processes related to the socio-economic life of the cities of Uzbekistan, the way of life of the population and their employment, increasing labor productivity. These studies focus to some extent on the transition situation of small cities to a market economy, the urbanization and demographic processes in them, and the social problems associated with the management of the social infrastructure of the economies of small and medium-sized cities in 1991-1992" .

In general, the amount and structure of capital determines the "place in the social space" or class position for the individual. The initial class division in the Burde scheme is at the intersection of large and small capital, but there is an additional difference between those with a large share of economic or cultural capital in each of these classes. So, when drawing up a map of the main social divisions in modern society, the concept of capital of Burde is given attention to the large number of individuals who are able to invest capital to what extent cities are, what degree of socialization processes are. Hence, in his work, Burde theoretically illuminates the observation of certain discrepancies between socialized individuals in the city and the village.

Anthony Giddens is considered one of the British scientists who made his worthy contribution to the enrichment of modern sociological knowledge. His work on sociology places a special emphasis on cities. "It focused on the issues of the traditional city, features of modern urbanism, the development of modern cities, the specificity of urban life, urbanistic ecology, urban theories, urbanism and social movement, the degradation of inner cities". "In the scientific-theoretical justification of Giddens' theory of systemic functionalism, interpersonal communication is that the environment that creates social communication in the exchange of information makes cities look at the quality of information space" .

He believes that by the end of the 20th century, statisticians and researchers of the society began to distinguish several large cities with small towns and local centers, which were considered overpopulated and much more cosmopolitan, and in which national societies that formed part of the same city also exerted their influence on other states. The growth of large cities was the result of population growth, as well as population migration-i.e. migration-from farmers, villages and small towns. For example, the area, which was almost uninhabited until 1830, was built by Chicago, which by 1900 had a population of more than 2 million people.

In our opinion, today people have information that allows them to reflect on the causes and consequences of their actions. People living in society are creating a collection of biographical narratives, social roles and lifestyles, and at the same time editing these life collections. But the increase in the types of choices causes a greater sense of freedom. Unlike societies in which members of society present such a social role, an individual creates his own social image. The specific way of life of cities has always served as a benchmark in the formation of the social image of the individual. When taken on this look, E.Giddens ' systematic functionalism is of particular importance in the development of small-town social infrastructure.

Also, today it is necessary to improve the planning and management mechanism of quantitative parameters of small cities. The implementation of small-town development programs, in an integrated approach to the formation of

target tasks for their transformation, requires a combination of the general efforts of an economist, architect, sociologist, environmentalist and other industry specialists.

Hence, the level of living of the population living in a small city, the social life of which is sharply different from that of large cities. These differences are visible in their lifestyle, labor activity, communal and domestic, cultural and cognitive opportunities. To reduce the existing differences in this regard, it is necessary to strengthen the material base of development of small cities. As a result, the comprehensive development of small cities, the improvement of conditions serve to keep the population active in various areas. In this: a) radical change in the appearance of a small city; b) in order to increase the level of the population of a small town spiritually-culturally, it is envisaged to achieve the most effective use of the economic opportunity to build cultural and art objects, library, theater, sports facilities.

C) regularly carry out targeted measures for the education of small-town residents, in particular, the culture of free time, the satisfaction of aesthetic needs;

D) the development and implementation of complex measures that will help the population find solutions to existing problems, raising a sense of patriotism towards their city, increasing public activity and increasing respect for the environment, aimed at improving life in it.

Industrial production is especially relevant in small cities, and the increase in production efficiency is also of deep importance. The implementation of current and priority tasks by means of orderly construction of housing infrastructure facilities, the development of raw materials, finished and semi-finished products for agriculture, the development of targeted programs aimed at their storage and strategic development of small cities, as well as the adoption of urban-type settlements will be solved. Therefore, the first of the terms of socio-economic modernization is the successful solution of the tasks set out in the program of strategic development of small cities.

In order to confirm this hypothesis, the respondents were asked "in what areas do you think it is necessary to strengthen practical measures mainly in the social support of the population living in small cities?" the majority (53.4%) of those who participated in the question answered that it was necessary to develop small and medium-sized businesses. The lowest (1.3%) respondent noted that new innovation projects should be implemented. So, the main part of the population of a small town believes that it is necessary to develop small and medium-sized businesses in the social support of the population. At the same time, they also showed a lack of knowledge, skills and skills in the implementation of new innovation projects. From these answers it follows that it shows the need to provide information with the population living in a small town by carrying out more explanatory and propaganda work on this issue.

The answers received on the questions asked above in this study the rules that reveal the essence and clear historical content of the social development of a small town serve as a theoretical basis for the Critical Study of information regarding the assessment of the economic and social role of the settlement in this area. It is the development of small cities that is directly and indirectly a prerequisite for the optimal social development of the whole society. In this study, it is advisable to focus on the following aspects, analyzing the theoretical basis of the social development of small cities:

1) scientific identification of the system of necessary social programs aimed at preventing small cities from lagging behind large cities, in which to create new opportunities for further optimization of the process of social development of the population;

2) research on the impact of all factors of urban expansion on the psychophysical state of citizens, analysis of social problems related to the support, promotion of modern cities, medical and biological;

3) to study the manifestation of social pathology in small cities, the structure and essence of pathology, to find a solution to the problems of maintaining the health of residents of this city in a scientific and practical way;

4) the comprehensive study of financial, social and psychological and religious problems of small cities and the system requires work.

According to the analysis of the results of the study, it can be noted that as one of the important conditions for the elevation of modern society, it is worth special attention to further improve the development of modern small cities and increase the social activity of the city's population in the structure of the integral socio-economic system of common large cities.

By expanding the economic capabilities of small cities in the social sphere, raising the lifestyle of the population indicates the connection between them and the issue of creating long necessary conditions. This connection assumes an integrated approach to the study of trends in the development of social processes in cities. Many aspects of this human life require scientifically based coordination. Scientific forecasting of various aspects of the life of the population in the development of new Uzbekistan in the context of new social economic relations should be carried out through the rational use of processes in small cities.

It is known that the inhabitants of the city are a socio-territorial community, which, like itself, are in appropriate relations with other communities and perform certain subjective functions in relation to the social system of the state. For this reason, the population of small towns in the Republic of Uzbekistan is manifested as a subject of reproduction and internal and external social relations. This subjective activity is carried out within a certain social environment, which determines the characteristics of the lifestyle of people as a whole. In our opinion, small cities are associated with a social factor that should be clearly defined in the management of the development of integration processes. This factor is due to the fact that on the one hand, the problem of managing social processes in a small city arises on the basis of the peculiarities and trends in the development of the lifestyle

of the population, and on the other, it involves a improving effect on some areas of people's life. The phenomenon of the way of life of people is inextricably linked without this tool and with reciprocal communication. In this context, all the changes that occur in the subject-object state system of social relations are manifested at the level of nature and society. It is for this reason that we tried to distinguish this integral indicator as a criterion for the development of the urban social system as a whole.

"It is natural that the essence and direction of this multifaceted and complex phenomenon, that is, the level of operationalism, is divided into certain areas in order to carry out the directed social development of the city based on the study of the lifestyle of the population. Because, this process is determined using different social indicators." According to our analysis, the main sphere of the subject's life was determined to be production and labor activity. Therefore, its qualitative and quantitative characteristics form the initial block of lifestyle indicators. However, the concept of a lifestyle will encompass not only a lifestyle characteristic of a particular territorial community, but also the conditions for their implementation. This requires a lot of attention to the analysis of signs and factors. That is, the specificity of the socio-political, economic, spiritual and other foundations of the sociality of the small-town system was fully analyzed as the environment for the existence of the subject. Finally, considering that the real carrier of the way of life is a certain individ, its life activity has carefully studied social communities of different levels (national, social, professional, status, age, etc.), the social behavior and stereotypes of a person in the specified cross section of parameters. This approach made it possible to fill the life of people, introducing into it a very important personal (subjective) component.

It will be necessary to constantly take into account that the presented panorama of objective determinants that determine the nature of the development of living conditions and activities of the population of small cities of our country is never enough for a comprehensive analysis of the dialectic of people's lifestyle.

Based on the results of the analysis of scientific research conducted before us, it can be said that the level of social trust and Social Protection play an important role as the main determining factor in the formation of a Real lifestyle. But they depend on many objective conditions for the development of the social environment. In addition, undoubtedly, the state of human health, the level of its psychological well-being, life directions and much more, is determined by objective conditions and phenomena in economic development. This is why, given the significant impact of the "personality component" on the way of life, this indicator is considered as a complex criterion for the development of the entire regional environment of human life.

In conclusion, the structure in which the main determinants are developed that determine the essence of human life are based on objective factors and indicators of the development of the social environment of a small city. A real lifestyle is a natural reflection of the state of a particular social space and trends in its development.

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